

Speculation on Role of Measurement Constraint on Quantum Free Particle Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 9, 2024

Shannon's entropy is calculated using probabilities, but what seems to be taken for granted perhaps, is the measurement constraints linked with these probabilities. For example, if one has uniform probability for a particle to be anywhere on an incline (two dimensional representation), this probability must be measured, (i.e. there is a constraint for the measurement to occur along the incline slope.) X and Y projections of this slope exist, but no measurements are performed there and so from the point of view of probability, these are math constructs. There is one measurement constraint in the problem, namely along the incline slope. (If one were to measure a shadow on the x axis, this would be an associated measurement with an associated entropy.)

For a quantum free particle, special probability (wavefunction) is given by $\exp(ip \cdot r) = \exp(ip_x x + i p_y y + i p_z z)$. If momentum lines along a line in (x,y,z) space, one may measure the full value by placing a target perpendicular to this line and noting impulse impact. This measurement, however, is linked with a measurement constraint as one considers motion along this line. If one considers uniform motion within a region \hbar/p (quantum wavelength) along this line, one may use this to calculate a free particle entropy: $-\ln(p/\hbar)$. It is physically possible, however, to make different measurements. For example, one may have a single target perpendicular to the x-axis (to measure p_x) or one perpendicular to the y-axis to measure p_y . These are physical measurements and one may consider $\exp(ip_x x)$ and $\exp(i p_y y)$ as corresponding probabilities, each leading to their own entropies, $-\ln(p_x/\hbar)$ and $-\ln(p_y/\hbar)$. The first question we ask is whether such projection probabilities are physical. We argue that they are in this note and that they are linked to conservation of momentum. We also point out, however, that just p_x is only part of p , $-\ln(\hbar/p_x)$ is not the full entropy. Thus, we suggest that one may have measurement based entropies.

Uniform Distribution on an Incline Slope

If one has a uniform distribution on a line, it is implicitly assumed that a particle is constrained to move along that line and so measurements occur along the line. One may have x and y projections of this line, but unless there are physical measurements linked with these projections, one would not consider a related probability. There could be a shadow on the x axis and one could calculate a probability for the shadow, but this is not the same as the probability for the actual particle constrained along the slope. Thus, if there is some kind of measurement along the x axis (or y axis), one may calculate an associated entropy, linked to the measurement, but realize that there is a different entropy linked to a different measurement, namely that of motion along the incline slope. Thus, we suggest that one may have measurement based entropies. It is possible for an associated entropy to demonstrate uncertainty linked with certain measurement constraints, while at the same time there may be a greater overall entropy because the particular measurement constraint ignores the full uncertainty in the system. For example, a shadow on the x axis only considers uncertainty in x, while ignoring the full uncertainty along the slope.

Quantum Free Particle

The quantum free particle is linked with the wavefunction (special probability) $\exp(ip \cdot r)$. Total momentum p may move along a line in (x,y,z) and strike a target perpendicular to this line creating a measurable impulse hit. Given the probability expression, one may consider uniform entropy along this line over a wavelength, i.e.

$$S = - \int_0^{\lambda} \frac{p}{\hbar} \ln\left(\frac{p}{\hbar}\right) dx = - \ln\left(\frac{P}{\hbar}\right) \quad ((1))$$

Instead of having a target along the line of motion, one may have one perpendicular to the x axis or to the y -axis. These targets only measure a portion of the impulse, i.e. they do not give the full momentum information. This is well-known. One may further associate special probabilities linked to these measurements, i.e. $\exp(ip_x x)$ or $\exp(ip_y y)$. These also don't give the full probability, but are associated probabilities linked to the measurement constraint.

The question we ask is: Are these associated probabilities physical, or in other words, are these associated Shannon's entropies meaningful? Certainly, these probabilities (and hence their entropies) are only part of the full picture, but why would one consider them in the first place? We suggest that the probabilities $\exp(ip_x x)$ and $\exp(ip_y y)$ are linked with conservation of entropy in the x and y directions and so are physical, i.e.

$$\int \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) \exp(-ip_3 x) \exp(-ip_4 x) dx = 0 \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 \neq p_3 + p_4 \quad ((2))$$

As a result, we suggest that the associated Shannon's entropies: $-\ln(p_x/\hbar)$ and $-\ln(p_y/\hbar)$, have physical meaning, but only capture entropy linked with the measurement and its constraint, i.e. motion along the x or y axis. Thus, there may be a measurement entropy which is not the full entropy in the picture. Simply because the target is perpendicular to the x -axis does not mean that there is not physical momentum (and hence spatial uncertainty) in the y direction. It is just not being measured. Thus, $-\ln(p_x/\hbar)$ is the momentum that is associated with a p_x measurement, but $-\ln(p/\hbar)$ is the full entropy.

One may easily link:

$$p^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2 \quad ((3))$$

The link between the associated entropies $-\ln(p(i)/\hbar)$ and the full entropy $-\ln(p/\hbar)$, however, is not given in a simple geometric manner.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we wish to point out that Shannon's entropy is based on probabilities which seem to be linked to specific measurements and the constraint linked to them. A particle moving along an incline slope has measurements constrained to the slope and hence a Shannon's entropy which reflects this measurement constraint. A shadow along the x axis, however, has

different probability and a different entropy, but it is an associated probability, not the full one. Thus, we suggest that there are measurement based entropies.

For the case of a quantum free particle with special probability $\exp(ip \cdot r)$, one has full momentum and entropy along the (x,y,z) line linked with the full momentum striking a target perpendicular to this line. The projections p_x and p_y , however, are real in the sense that they describe the impulse with a target along the x and y axes respectively. The probabilities $\exp(ip_x x)$ and $\exp(ip_y y)$ are linked with these measurements, but are constrained by the measurement, i.e. they are not the full uncertainty in the situation. We suggest that they are nevertheless physical for these measurements because they are linked with conservation of momentum in the x and y directions which is key when the interactions occur. Thus, one may write associated entropies $-\ln(p(i)/\hbar)$, linked to measurement constraints, but has to realize that due to such constraints, these may not be the full uncertainty or entropy. A measurement which does not lose some p information (i.e. captures it all) will be linked with the full free particle entropy: $-\ln(p/\hbar)$.